

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Rational design of nutrient sensing and growth factor inhibition for resistance in breast cancer following treatment with endocrine therapy.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe here a kinetic study of the transcriptional response to endocrine therapy in vitro and in vivo.

1 **Results**

2 GSE241764

3 We measured total transcription in MCF7 cells at 15 minutes, 1 hour, 6 hours, and 24 hours

4 I. Nutrient sensing and energy

5 Sestrin
6 TBC
7 TBD
8 AKT

9 II. Secretory pathway genes

10 Rab
11 Rab27B
12 Rab3d

13 III. Solute carriers

14 IV. ABC MDR channels

15 V. Kinase and phosphatase compensatory signaling targets

16 MAPK family

17 Other kinases

18 CDK17
19 CDK18

20 Phosphatases

21 VI. Ribosome pathway

22 ● The data indicated that validation of the genes described in a genetic screen to blindly identify
23 genes activated in resistance in vitro or in vivo when comparing the tumor transcriptomes of humans with
24 luminal breast cancers when comparing genes activated most significantly, would enable and support the
25 design of precision based, combinatorial targeting strategy targeting compensatory signaling mechanisms
26 associated with resistance to endocrine therapy through escalation and activation of growth factor and
27 nutrient sensing pathways.

28 ● Design of the approach was guided by systems biologic-aided selection of a minimal set of
components activated in resistance whose blockade is designed to address resistant behaviors by the
tumor following treatment with an endocrine therapy agent. This minimal set of components, delivered
together with combined 2 compensatorily activated kinase targets, includes a TBC and TSC family gene, a
selected gene from both PI3K and AKT pathways, and four other genes selected from secretory and
trafficking pathways gene families that function in concert or simultaneously with nutrient sensing and
energy signaling by mTOR, PI3K and AKT: a CCDC family gene, a Sec family genes, a Vps family gene,
and a Rab family gene.

1 • We determined whether any genes whose expression was identified by kinetic analysis of
2 transcription share between cells treated with either tamoxifen or fulvestrant as activated in response to
3 chemotherapeutic hormone deprivation by studying total transcription by RNA-sequencing in tamoxifen
4 resistant breast cancer cell clones.

5 GSE241654: ET resistance screen (MCF7 tamoxifen)

6 • Genes induced by hormone deprivation from 15 minutes to 24 hours in response to tamoxifen or
7 fulvestrant, if not induced solely as a transient response, were likely candidates as component genes in
8 the general compensatory response to chemotherapeutic (endocrine therapy) challenge (“resistance”).

8 TBC1D24

9 Rab30
10 Rab40B
11 Rab3D

12 Rps
13 19

14 **CDK**

15 18
16 14
17 13
18 19

19 **Vps**

20 54

- Cog7 and Cog8 were activated in this dataset but not Cog2
- Stx6 was activated in this dataset; Stx16 was marginally activated

21 **Sec**

22 Sec23b

23 ABCC5

24 ABCB7

25 CCDC6

26 MAP4K5

27 MAP3K2

28 **PI3K**

PIK3R3

PIK3R2

1 • We used a collection of separate cell culture based resistance systems (GSE241942) to validate
2 the identity of a gene as a therapeutic target for blockade of growth factor and nutrient sensing pathways
3 in endocrine therapy breast cancer.

4 GSE241942

- 5 • TBC1D4
- 6 • TBC1D10B
- 7 • TBC1D24

8 GSE125738

9 GSE59515

10 GSE104050

11 GSE165571

12 GSE159968

13 GSE77948

14 GSE43809

15 GSE221439

16 GSE80077

17 CDK17

18 • We queried a fourth dataset, an in vivo tumor transcriptome comparison that identified genes
19 important for driving resistance by comparing tumor transcriptome based on patient outcome following
20 endocrine therapy for hormone receptor positive breast cancer, to determine whether genes identified in
21 vitro transcriptome based expression screens were actual targets of the resistance programs in humans
22 with breast cancer treated with a hormone deprivation chemotherapeutic.

23 GSE33658: Patients treated with endocrine therapy for hormone receptor positive breast cancer
24 (anastrozole and fulvestrant),

25 CDK17

26 Rab3D

27 TBC1D24

28 CCDC6

ABC1F1

ABCA3

ABCB8

ABCC5

ABCB7

ABCE1

ABCA7

1	<u>MAP3K2</u>
2	MAP3K12
3	MAP4K5
4	MAPK13
5	MAPK9
6	STK36
7	STK39
8	STK32B
9	RPS6KA6
10	<u>RPS19</u>
11	RPS25
12	SEC
13	61A2
14	<u>23B</u>
15	13
16	63
17	61A1
18	Vps
19	13D
20	26B
21	37B
22	52
23	<u>54</u>
24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vps54 was predicted to interact with Stx6 and Stx16, which were both activated in this cohort • Vps54 was also predicted to interact with Cog7, Cog8 and Cog2, which were both activated in this cohort
25	Ccdc
26	117
27	167
28	85C
29	<u>6</u>
30	22
31	96
32	125
33	Rab
34	14
35	<u>3D</u>
36	1B
37	15
38	24

1 CDK5

2 1

7

3 2

17

4 4

12

5 19

6 Other ET resistance associated in vitro systems:

7 GSE230362: ESR1 Y537S

8 GSE153033: ESR1 Y537N

9 GSE249723: ESR1-SOX9

10
11 II. Genes conserved in expression were likely still important, but differently, indicating a general requirement for the molecule in hormone receptor positive breast cancer.

12 Notes:

13 The following information was consulted for in vivo or in vitro validation:

14 GSE241654

15 NR2F2, NR1D2, NR3C1, NCOA1, (decreased) NRIP1, NR2C1, NCOA2, NR2D2, NR2F1, (decreased)
16 NR5A2, NR3C2, and NCOA5 were

17
18 ESR1 mutants expressed in patients with breast cancer activated GREB1 expression in breast cancer
19 cells in vitro in the absence of estrogen.

20 ESR1 fusions found in the tumors of patients with breast cancer activate GREB1 expression in xenograft
21 models in vivo.

22 We measured total transcription in the tumors of four separate patient cohorts, each composed of
23 hormone positive receptor breast cancer patients whose treatment response or disease outcome had
24 been identified as a complete response, having residual disease, having a partial response, with stable
25 disease, or having disease progression. We used this data to measure tumor gene expression at the
26 transcriptome level and blindly identify genes whose increased expression was. We hypothesized this
27 method would allow us to identify nuclear factors that had become activated during relapse or resistance
28 to endocrine therapy and cooperated with GREB1 and/or ESR1 in resistance in hormone positive breast
cancer.

1 Clinical Data (Translational)

2 Letrozole resistance: GSE146911

3 GSE48905: In a cohort of patients treated with endocrine therapy (fulvestrant) for HR+ breast cancer,
4 increased expression of NRIP1, NFIL3, NCOA7, NCOA1, NCOA2, NR3C1, NR4A3 and NR1H3 were
5 significantly correlated inferior treatment outcome (tumor transcriptomes of patients were measured and
6 compared based on treatment response: partial response, stable disease, or disease progression).

7 GSE33658:

8 In a group of patients treated with endocrine therapy for hormone receptor positive breast cancer
9 (anastrozole and fulvestrant), increased expression of NCOA5, NCOA1, and NCOA3 was associated with
10 treatment failure (disease progression).

11 We identified NCOA3 here as a GREB1 binding partner using protein-protein interaction using proteomic
12 techniques.

13 GSE25055:

14 In HR+ patients treated with endocrine therapy (mixed luminal A and luminal B subtype), residual disease
15 (RD) was associated with activation of NR2A1, NR4A3, NR3C1, NCOA2, NR1H3, NR1D2 and to a lesser
16 extent, NCOA1.

17 GSE198650:

18 In HR+ patients treated with endocrine therapy, NCOA2 and NCOA3 were activated in patients with
19 disease progression (PD). NR6A1 was activated in the tumors of patients with disease progression, as
20 was NR5A2 and NRIP1, but to a lesser extent. The expression of NCOA2/3, NR6A1, NR5A2 and NRIP1
21 was correlated with a specific clinical outcome, treatment failure in hormone positive patients treated with
22 endocrine therapy, and was identified blindly (transcriptome-level).

23 We identified NR5A2 and NCOA3 here as GREB1 binding partners using protein-protein interaction using
24 proteomic techniques.
25
26
27
28